

**A SUMMARY OF THE CURRENT SYSTEMATIC STATUS OF THE
GENUS ALLIUM L. AND THE SPECIES A.BOTSANZEVII**

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Annotation. This paper involves an information on the scientific research aimed at the assessment and characterization of mountain pastures and the improvement of mountain pastures in crisis, the current systematic status of the species *Allium botschanzwvii* Kamelin, including the taxonomic status of the list of species belonging to the *Allium L.* genus.

Keywords. *Allium botschanzwvii* Kamelin., taxon, flora, medicine plant, endemic, taxon, ecology, anthropogenic.

Introduction. We can note that some decrees were adopted to improve the condition of endemic plants such as No. 299 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 23, 2018 “On measures to further improve the procedure for determining the boundaries of administrative-territorial units, delimiting land resources and conducting geobotanical research in pastures and hayfields” and No. 1034 of December 19, 2018 “On Measures for the Preparation, Publication and Management of the Red Book” and other regulatory legal documents, it should not be forgotten that it is the duty of every citizen to protect rare and endemic plant species distributed in mountain ranges and preserve the area of each species in the gene pool during climate change.

Scientific research aimed at evaluating mountain pastures and determining their characteristics and improving mountain pastures in crisis is carried out in leading scientific centers and higher education institutions of the world, including Wake Forest University (USA), Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research (Bulgaria), Albrecht von Haller Institute of Plant Sciences (Germany), Tokyo University of Agriculture and Technology (Japan), Baekdudaegan National Arboretum (Korea), Aarhus University (Denmark), Cold and Arid Regions Environmental and Engineering Research Institute (China), Institute of Botany and Phytointroduction (Kazakhstan) and Botany institute (Uzbekistan).

Determination of phytocenotic diversity of mountain pastures, revealing their historical formation, assessment of changes in pasture communities under the influence of various factors, and research on preservation of mountain pastures have resulted in a number of results, including: rare types of pastures in the arid mountain region, their effective preservation measures were developed and the pasture management system was improved (Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgaria), steppe pastures, their origin and modern formation were determined (Albrecht von Haller Institute of Plant Sciences, Germany), effective methods of mountain forest restoration were developed (Baekdudaegan National Arboretum, Korea), the structure of mountain meadows of the middle climate and the effects of climate change and livestock on them were evaluated (Wake Forest University, USA), the characteristics of the crisis of alpine pastures and its driving factors were based (Cold and Arid Regions Environmental and Engineering Research Institute, China).

On the assessment of the state of pastures and their restoration in various natural regions of Central Asia were conducted researches by scientists such as N.T. Nechaeva (1958, 1962), L.P. Sinkovsky (1959), I.F. Momotov (1962), V.A. Burygin, L.E. Markova (1975), R.S. Wernick, T. Rakhimova (1982), O.Kh. Hasanov and T. Rakhimova (1996, 2000, 2003, 2006), Z.Sh. Shamsutdinov (2015), H.F. Shomurodov (2018).

Information on the flora, phytocenotic structure, ecology of the pastures of the mountain and sub-mountain areas of the Kashkadarya basin was reflected in the research works of V.A. Komarov (1891-1893), B.A. Fedchenko (1913), M.G. Popov (1925), S.N. Kudryashov (1941, 1950), E.P. Korovin (1934, 1956, 1962), K.Z. Zakirov (1955), I.I. Granitov, A.D. Pyataeva (1956, 1959), I.F. Momotov, A.D. Lee (1965), A.N. Babushkin (1964), E.M. Demurina (1975), S.M. Mustafaev (1966), U. Allanazarova (1969), A.Z. Genusov (1972), O.Kh. Khasanov (1972), N.I. Akzhigitova (1976), R.V. Kamelin (1979), E. Ashurov (1988), T. Norbobaeva (1990), T.V. Ovchinnikova (1995), F.Kh. Dzhangurazov (1965), B.E. Khujamkulov (1998), F. Khasanov (2013, 2014) and others.

Uzbekistan has a rich flora of vascular plants consisting of about 5500 species. The genus *Allium* L. is represented by 112 species and 4 subspecies, which ranks third among highly polymorphic genera (*Astragalus* L. and *Cousinia* Cass.). The use of particularly tasty *Allium* species has a long tradition in Central Asia and deep historical roots. People living in desert and mountain areas collect onions and leaves and use them to prepare and sell special dishes. Residents of the city buy the necessary plant material from local markets. Traditionally, people have grown not only *A. cepa* L., *A. sativum* L. in their home gardens (sometimes *A. porrum* L., *A. ramosum* L.), but also they grow rarely wild species (*A. suworowii*, *A. oschaninii*, *A. Pskemense*).

During 2002-2006, several studies were conducted in the Western Tien-Shan, Western Pamir Aloy mountain zone, as well as in the Kyzylkum desert. About 25 men were interviewed about the use of wild alliums for food and medicine. Often the old sages and shepherds had a good knowledge of the use of each type of wild onion in the village. Knowledge of such information is greatly reduced, as only a few elderly people in each village are able to provide any real information.

Kashkadarya province includes the Karshi depression in southern Uzbekistan, bordered in the north by the mountains of Koratepa, Zarafshan ranges, Zirabulok, and

Ziyevuddin; in the east – by the foothills of the southwestern part of the Gisar ridge [2]. As a result of the study, we analyzed the plant species of mountain pastures and determined the current state of pastures in the Kashkadarya Basin.

We interpret the taxonomic position of the list of species belonging to the *Allium* L. category as follows: Angiosperms – Asparagales Link. – Amaryllidaceae J.St.-Hil. – *Allium* L. – *Allium botschantzevii* Kamelin.

Following species are currently taxonomically assigned to the genus:

Allium aaseae Ownbey, *Allium abbasii* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium abramsii* (Traub) McNeal, *Allium acidoides* Stearn, *Allium aciphyllum* J.M.Xu, *Allium acuminatum* Hook, *Allium acutiflorum* Loisel, *Allium aegilicum* Tzanoud, *Allium aeginiense* Brullo, Giusso & Terrasi, *Allium aetnense* Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium affine* Ledeb, *Allium afghanicum* Wendelbo, *Allium aflatunense* B.Fedtsch, *Allium agarmyschicum* N.Friesen & Seregin, *Allium agrigentinum* Brullo & Pavone, *Allium akaka* S.G.Gmel. ex Schult. & Schult.f, *Allium aksekiense* Özhatay, Koyuncu & E.Kaya, *Allium alabasicum* Y.Z.Zhao, *Allium aladaghense* Memariani & Joharchi, *Allium alaicum* Vved, *Allium alamutense* Razyfard, Zarre & R.M.Fritsch, *Allium albiflorum* Omelczuk, *Allium albotunicatum* O.Schwarz, *Allium albovianum* Vved, *Allium alekii* R.M.Fritsch & M.V.Agab, *Allium alexandrae* Vved, *Allium alexeianum* Regel *Allium amphibolum* Ledeb, *Allium amplexans* Torr, *Allium anacoleum* Hand-Mazz, *Allium anatolicum* Özhatay & B.Mathew, *Allium anceps* Kellogg, *Allium angolensis* Baker, *Allium angulosum* L, *Allium anisopodium* Ledeb, *Allium anisotepalum* Vved, *Allium antalyense* Eren, Çinbilgel & Parolly, *Allium antiatlanticum* Emb. & Maire, *Allium anzalonei* Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium apergii* Trigas, Iatroú & Tzanoud, *Allium apolloniensis* Biel, Kit Tan & Tzanoud, *Allium apulum* Brullo, Guglielmo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium archeotrichon* Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium arkitense* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium arlgirdense* Blakelock, *Allium armenum* Boiss. & Kotschy, *Allium armerioides* Boiss, *Allium aroides* Popov & Vved, *Allium*

arsuzense Eker & Koyuncu, Allium artemisietorum Eig & Feinbrun, Allium asarense R.M.Fritsch & Matin, Allium ascalonicum L, Allium aschersonianum Barbey, Allium asclepiadeum Bornm, Allium asirense B.Mathew, Allium asperiflorum Miscz. ex Grossh, Allium assadii Seisums, Allium atropurpureum Waldst. & Kit, Allium atrorubens S.Watson, Allium atosanguineum Schrenk, Allium atroviolaceum Boiss, Allium aucheri Boiss, Allium auriculatum Kunth, Allium austrodanubiense N.Friesen & Seregin, Allium austroiranicum R.M.Fritsch, Allium austrokyushuense M.Hotta, Allium austrosibiricum Frizen, Allium austrosi-biricum N.Friesen, Allium autumnale P.H.Davis, Allium autumniflorum F.O.Khass. & Akhani, Allium azaurense Gomb, Allium aznavense R.M.Fritsch, Allium azutavicum Kotukhov, Allium backhousianum Regel, Allium baekdusanense Y.N.Lee, Allium baeticum Boiss, Allium bajtulinii Bajtenov & I.I.Kamenetskaya, Allium bakhtiaricum Regel, Allium balansae Boiss, Allium balkhanicum (R.M.Fritsch & F.O.Khass.) R.M.Fritsch, Allium baluchis-tanicum Wendelbo, Allium barszczewskii Lipsky, Allium barthianum Asch. & Schweinf, Allium basalticum Fragman & R.M.Fritsch, Allium bassiten-se J.Thiebaut, Allium baytopiorum Kollmann & Özhatay, Allium beesianum W.W.Sm, Allium bekeczalicum Lazkov, Allium bellulum Prokh, Allium bidentatum Fisch. ex Prokh. & Ikonn.-Gal, Allium bigelovii S.Watson, Allium bilgeae Yild, Allium bingoelense Yild. & Kiliç, Allium birkin-shawii Mouterde, Allium bisceptrum S.Watson, Allium bisotunen-se R.M.Fritsch, Allium blandum Wall, Allium blomfieldianum Asch. & Schweinf, Allium boissieri Regel, Allium bolanderi S.Watson, Allium bornmuelleri Hayek, Allium borszczowii Regel, Allium botschantzevii Kamelin, Allium bourgeauii Rech.f, Allium brachyodon Boiss, Allium brachyscapum Vved, Allium brachyspathum Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, Allium bracteolatum Wendelbo, Allium brandegeei S.Watson, Allium brevicaule Boiss. & Balansa, Allium brevidens Vved, Allium breviden-tatum F.Z.Li, Allium

brevidentiforme Vved, *Allium brevipes* Ledeb, *Allium breviscapum* Stapf, *Allium brevistylum* S.Watson, *Allium brulloi* Salmeri, *Allium brussalisii* Tzanoud. & Kypr, *Allium bucharicum* Regel, *Allium bungei* Boiss, *Allium burjaticum* Frizen, *Allium burjaticum* N.Friesen, *Allium burlewii* Davidson, *Allium caeruleum* Pall, *Allium caesioides* Wendelbo, *Allium caesium* Schrenk, *Allium caespitosum* Siev. ex Bong. & C.A. Mey, *Allium calabrum* (N.Terracc.) Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium calamarophilum* Phitos & Tzanoud, *Allium callidiction* C.A.Mey. ex Kunth, *Allium callimischon* Link, *Allium calocephalum* Wendelbo, *Allium calyptratum* Boiss, *Allium campanulatum* S.Watson, *Allium canariense* (Regel) N.Friesen & P.Schönfelder, *Allium candargyi* Karavok. & Tzanoud, *Allium candolleanum* Albov, *Allium capitellatum* Boiss, *Allium cappadocicum* Boiss. & Balansa, *Allium caput-medusae* Airy Shaw, *Allium cardiostemon* Fisch. & C.A.Mey, *Allium carinatum* L, *Allium carmeli* Boiss, *Allium carolihenrici* Wendelbo, *Allium carolinianum* Redouté, *Allium caspium* (Pall.) M.Bieb, *Allium cassium* Boiss, *Allium castellanense* (Garbari, Miceli & Raimondo) Brullo, Guglielmo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium cathodicarpum* Wendelbo, *Allium cepa* L, *Allium cephalonicum* Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium cernuum* Roth, *Allium chalcophengos* Airy Shaw, *Allium chal-kii* Tzanoud. & Kollmann, *Allium chamaemoly* L, *Allium chamaespathum* Boiss, *Allium chamarense* M.M.Ivanova, *Allium changduense* J.M.Xu, *Allium chienchuanense* J.M.Xu, *Allium chinense* G.Don, *Allium chitralicum* F.T.Wang & Tang, *Allium chiwui* F.T.Wang & Tang, *Allium chloranthum* Boiss, *Allium chloroneurum* Boiss, *Allium chlorotepalum* R.M.Fritsch & M.Jaeger, *Allium chodsabakirganicum* Gaffarov & Turak, *Allium choriotepalum* Wendelbo, *Allium chorkessaricum* F.O.Khass. & Tojibaev, *Allium chrysantherum* Boiss. & Reut, *Allium chrysanthum* Regel, *Allium chrysocephalum* Regel, *Allium chychka-nense* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium circassicum* Kolak, *Allium circinatum* Sieber, *Allium circumflexum* Wendelbo, *Allium cisferganense* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium cithae-ronis* Bogdanovic, C.Brullo, Brullo,

Giusso, Musarella & Salmeri, *Allium clathratum* Ledeb, *Allium clausum* Vved, *Allium clivorum* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium columbianum* (Ownbey & Mingrone) P.M.Peterson, Annable & Rieseberg, *Allium commutatum* Guss, *Allium condensatum* Turcz, *Allium confragosum* Vved, *Allium consanguineum* Kunth, *Allium constrictum* (Ownbey & Mingrone) P.M.Peterson, Annable & Rieseberg, *Allium convallarioides* Grossh, *Allium cornutum* Clementi, *Allium cornutum* Vis, *Allium corsicum* Jauzein, J.M.Tison, Deschâtres & H.Couderc, *Allium coryi* M.E.Jones, *Allium costatovaginatatum* Kamelin & Levichev, *Allium crameri* Asch. & Boiss, *Allium cratericola* Eastw, *Allium crenulatum* Wiegand, *Allium cretaceum* N.Friesen & Seregin, *Allium crispum* Greene, *Allium cristophii* Trautv, *Allium croaticum* Bogdanovic, Brullo, Mitic & Salmeri, *Allium cucullatum* Wendelbo, *Allium cupani* Raf, *Allium cupanii* Raf, *Allium cupuliferum* Regel, *Allium curtum* Boiss. & Gaill, *Allium cuthbertii* Small, *Allium cyaneum* Regel, *Allium cyathophorum* Bureau & Franch, *Allium cyprium* Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium cyrilli* Ten, *Allium czelghauricum* Bordz, *Allium daghestanicum* Grossh, *Allium damascenum* Feinbrun, *Allium daninianum* Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium darwasicum* Regel, *Allium dasyphyllum* Vved, *Allium decaisnei* C.Presl, *Allium deciduum* Özhatay & Kollmann, *Allium decipiens* Fisch. ex Schult. & Schult.f, *Allium decoratum* Turginov & Tojibaev, *Allium delicatulum* Siev. ex Schult. & Schult.f, *Allium dentigerum* Prokh, *Allium denudatum* Redouté, *Allium derderianum* Regel, *Allium deserti-syriaci* Feinbrun, *Allium desertorum* Forssk, *Allium diabolense* (Ownbey & Aase ex Traub) McNeal, *Allium dich-lamydeum* Greene, *Allium dictyon* H.St.John, *Allium dictyoprasum* C.A.Mey. ex Kunth, *Allium dictyoscordum* Vved, *Allium dilatatum* Zahar, *Allium dinsmorei* Rech.f, *Allium diomedeam* Brullo, Guglielmo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium dirphianum* Brullo, Guglielmo, Pavone, Salmeri & Terrasi, *Allium djimilense* Boiss. ex Regel, *Allium dodecadontum* Vved, *Allium dodecanesi* Karavok. & Tzanoud, *Allium dolichomischum* Vved, *Allium*

dolichostylum Vved, Allium dolichova-ginatum R.M.Fritsch, Allium douglasii Hook, Allium drepanophyllum Vved, Allium drobovi Vved, Allium drummondii Regel, Allium drusorum Feinbrun, Allium dshungaricum Vved, Allium dumetorum Feinbrun & Szel, Allium duran-goense Traub, Allium dyctioprasum C.A.Mey. ex Kunth, Allium ebusitanum Font Quer, Allium eduardi Stearn ex Airy Shaw, Allium efeae Özhatay & I.Genç, Allium egorovae M.V.Agab. & Ogan, Allium ekeri E.Kaya & Koçyigit, Allium ekimianum Eksi, Koyuncu & Özkan, Allium elburzense Wendelbo, Allium eldivanense Özhatay, Allium elegans Drobow, Allium elegantulum Kitag, Allium ellisii Hook.f, Allium elmaliense Deniz & Sümbül, Allium elmendorffii M.E.Jones ex Ownbey, Allium enginii Özhatay & B.Mathew, Allium erdelii Zucc, Allium eremoprasum Vved, Allium ericetorum Thore, Allium eriocoleum Vved, Allium ertugrulii Demir. & Uysal, Allium erubescens K.Koch, Allium erythraeum Griseb, Allium erzincanicum Özhatay & Kandemir, Allium esfahanicum R.M.Fritsch, Allium esfandiarrii Marin, Allium euboicum Rech.f, Allium eugeni Vved, Allium eulae Cory ex T.M.Howard, Allium eurotophilum Wiggins, Allium eusperma Airy Shaw, Allium exaltatum (Meikle) Brullo, Pavone, Salmeri & Venora, Allium exile Boiss. & Orph, Allium falcifolium Hook. & Arn, Allium fanjingshanense C.D.Yang & G.Q.Gou, Allium fantasmense Traub, Allium farctum Wendelbo, Allium farreri Stearn, Allium fasciculatum Rendle, Allium favosum Zahar, Allium fedtschenkoi Nábelek, Allium feinbergii Oppenh, Allium ferganicum Vved, Allium fethiyense Özhatay & B.Mathew, Allium fibriferum Wendelbo, Allium fibrillum M.E.Jones, Allium filidens Regel, Allium filidentiforme Vved, Allium fimbriatum S.Watson, Allium fistulosum L, Allium flavellum Vved, Allium flavescens Besser, Allium flavidum Ledeb, Allium flavovirens Regel, Allium flavum L, Allium formosum Sennikov & Lazkov, Allium forrestii Diels, Allium francinae Brullo & Pavone, Allium fraseri (Ownbey) Shinnery, Allium frigidum Boiss. & Heldr, Allium fritschii F.O.Khass. & Yengal,

Allium funckiifolium Hand. Mazz, Allium furkatii R.M.Fritsch, Allium fuscoviolaceum Fomin, Allium fuscum Waldst. & Kit, Allium gabardaghense Firat, Allium galanthum Kar. & Kir, Allium galileum Brullo, Guglielmo, Pavone & Salmeri, Allium garba-rii Peruzzi, Allium garganicum Brullo, Pavone, Salmeri & Terrasi, Allium gasyunense Mouterde, Allium geyeri S.Watson, Allium giganteum Regel, Allium gilgiticum F.T.Wang & Tang, Allium gillii Wendelbo, Allium glaciale Vved, Allium glandulosum Link & Otto, Allium glomeratum Prokh, Allium glumaceum Boiss. & Hausskn, Allium goekyigitii Ekim, H.Duman & Güner, Allium gomphrenoides Boiss. & Heldr, Allium gooddingii Ownbey, Allium gorumsense (Regel) Boiss, Allium goulimyti Tzanoud, Allium gracillimum Vved, Allium gramineum K.Koch, Allium grande Lipsky, Allium graveolens (R.M.Fritsch) R.M.Fritsch, Allium greuteri Brullo & Pavone, Allium griffithianum Boiss, Allium grisellum J.M.Xu, Allium grosii Font Quer, Allium guanxianense J.M.Xu, Allium guatemalense Traub, Allium gubanovii Kamelin, Allium guicciardii Heldr, Allium gunibicum Misch. ex Grossh, Allium gusaricum Regel, Allium guttatum Steven, Allium gypsaceum Popov & Vved, Allium gypsodictyum Vved, Allium haemanthoides Boiss. & Reut. ex Regel, Allium haematochiton S.Watson, Allium hamedanense R.M.Fritsch, Allium hamri-nense Hand.-Mazz, Allium haneltii F.O.Khass. & R.M.Fritsch, Allium haussknechtii Nábelek, Allium hedgei Wendelbo, Allium heldreichii Boiss, Allium helicophyllum Vved, Allium hemisphaericum (Sommier) Brullo, Allium henryi C.H.Wright, Allium herderianum Regel, Allium hermoneum (Kollmann & Shmida) Brullo, Guglielmo, Pavone & Salmeri, Allium heteronema F.T.Wang & Tang, Allium hexaceras Vved, Allium hickmanii Eastw, Allium hierosolymorum Regel, Allium hindukuschense Kamelin & Seisums, Allium hintoniorum B.L.Turner, Allium hirtovaginum Candargy, Allium hissaricum Vved, Allium hoffmanii Ownbey ex Traub, Allium hollandicum R.M.Fritsch, Allium hookeri Thwaites, Allium hooshidaryae Mashayekhi, Zarre & R.M.Fritsch, Allium

horvatii Lovric, *Allium howellii* Eastw, *Allium huber-morathii* Kollmann, Özhatay & Koyuncu, *Allium humile* Kunth, *Allium huntiae* Traub, *Allium hyalinum* Curran, *Allium hymenorrhizum* Ledeb, *Allium hymettium* Boiss. & Heldr, *Allium hypsistum* Stearn, *Allium ilgazense* Özhatay, *Allium iliense* Regel, *Allium inaequale* Janka, *Allium inconspicuum* Vved, *Allium incrustatum* Vved, *Allium inderiense* Fisch. ex Bunge, *Allium inops* Vved, *Allium insubricum* Boiss. & Reut, *Allium insufficiens* Vved, *Allium integerrimum* Zahar, *Allium intradarvazicum* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium inutile* Makino, *Allium ionandrum* Wendelbo, *Allium ionicum* Brullo & Tzanoud, *Allium iranicum* (Wendelbo) Wendelbo, *Allium iranshahrii* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium isakulii* R.M.Fritsch & F.O.Khass, *Allium isauricum* Hub-Mor. & Wendelbo, *Allium israeliticum* Fragman & R.M.Fritsch, *Allium ivasczenkoae* Kotukhov, *Allium jacquemontii* Kunth, *Allium jaege-ri* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium jakuticum* Sinitsyna & N.Friesen, *Allium jaxarticum* Vved, *Allium jepsonii* (Ownbey & Aase ex Traub) S.S.Denison & McNeal, *Allium jesdianum* Boiss. & Buhse, *Allium jodanthum* Vved, *Allium joharchii* F.O.Khass. & Memariani, *Allium jubatum* J.F.Macbr, *Allium jucundum* Vved, *Allium julducicola* Regel, *Allium julduciculum* Regel, *Allium julianum* Brullo, Gangale & Uzunov, *Allium junceum* Sm, *Allium kandemirii* I.Genç & Özhatay, *Allium karacae* Koyuncu, *Allium karamanoglu* Koyuncu & Kollmann, *Allium karataviense* Regel, *Allium karelinii* Poljak, *Allium karistanum* Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium karyeteini* Post, *Allium kaschianum* Regel, *Allium kastambulense* Kollmann, *Allium kasteki* Popov, *Allium kayae* Özhatay & Koyuncu, *Allium kazerouni* Parsa, *Allium kermesinum* Rchb, *Allium keusgenii* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium kharputense* Freyn & Sint, *Allium khozratense* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium kiiense* (Murata) Hir.Takah.bis & M.Hotta, *Allium kingdonii* Stearn, *Allium kirilovii* N.Friesen & Seregin, *Allium kirindicum* Bornm, *Allium klarputense* Freyn & Sint, *Allium koelzii* (Wendelbo) Perss. & Wendelbo, *Allium koenigianum* Grossh, *Allium kokanicum* Regel, *Allium kollmannianum* Brullo, Pavone &

Salmeri, *Allium komarowii* Lipsky, *Allium kopetdagense* Vved, *Allium kopsedorum* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium koreanum* H.J.Choi & B.U.Oh, *Allium korolkowi* Regel, *Allium kossoricum* Fomin, *Allium kotschyi* Boiss, *Allium koyuncui* H.Duman & Özhatay, *Allium kuhrangense* Akhavan, Saeidi & R.M.Fritsch, *Allium kuhsorkhense* R.M.Fritsch & Joharchi, *Allium kujukense* Vved, *Allium kunthianum* Vved, *Allium kuramense* F.O.Khass. & N.Friesen, *Allium kurdistanicum* Maroofi & R.M.Fritsch, *Allium kurssanovii* Popov, *Allium kurtzianum* Asch. & Sint. ex Kollmann, *Allium kwakense* (R.M.Fritsch) R.M.Fritsch, *Allium kysylkumi* Kamelin, *Allium lachnophyllum* Paine, *Allium lacunosum* S.Watson, *Allium lagarophyllum* Brullo, Pavone & Tzanoud, *Allium lalesaricum* Freyn & Bornm, *Allium lamondiae* Wendelbo, *Allium lasiophyllum* Vved, *Allium latifolium* Jaub. & Spach, *Allium lazikkiyense* Koçyigit, Özhatay & E.Kaya, *Allium ledebourianum* Schult. & Schult.f, *Allium lehmannianum* Merckl. ex Bunge, *Allium lehmannii* Lojac, *Allium lemmonii* S.Watson, *Allium lenkoranicum* Misch. ex Grossh, *Allium leptomorphum* Vved, *Allium leucocephalum* Turcz. ex Ledeb, *Allium leucosphaerum* Aitch. & Baker, *Allium libani* Boiss, *Allium lilacinum* Klotzsch, *Allium liliputianum* Koçyigit, Özhatay & E.Kaya, *Allium lineare* L, *Allium linearifolium* H.J.Choi & B.U.Oh, *Allium lipskyanum* Vved, *Allium listera* Stearn, *Allium litardierei* J.-M.Tison, *Allium litvinovii* Drobow ex Vved, *Allium lojaconoi* Brullo, Lanfr. & Pavone, *Allium longanum* Pamp, *Allium longevaginatum* Wendelbo, *Allium longicol-lum* Wendelbo, *Allium longifolium* (Kunth) Spreng, *Allium longipapil-latum* R.M.Fritsch & Matin, *Allium longiradiatum* (Regel) Vved, *Allium longise-palum* Bertol, *Allium longistylum* Baker, *Allium lopadusanum* Bartolo, Brullo & Pavone, *Allium loratum* Baker, *Allium lusitanicum* Lam, *Allium luteolum* Halácsy, *Allium lutescens* Vved, *Allium lycaonicum* Siehe ex Hayek, *Allium maackii* (Maxim.) Prokh. ex Kom, *Allium macedonicum* Zahar, *Allium machme-lianum* Post, *Allium macleanii* Baker, *Allium macranthum* Baker, *Allium macrochaetum* Boiss. &

Hauskn, *Allium macropetalum* Rydb, *Allium macros-temon* Bunge, *Allium macrostylum* Regel, *Allium macrum* S.Watson, *Allium madidum* S.Watson, *Allium maghrebinum* Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium mahneshanense* Razyfard, Zarre & R.M.Fritsch, *Allium mairei* H.Lév, *Allium majus* Vved, *Allium makrianum* C.Brullo, Brullo, Giusso & Salmeri, *Allium malyshevii* N.Friesen, *Allium maniaticum* Brullo & Tzanoud, *Allium mannii* Traub & T.M.Howard, *Allium maowenense* J.M.Xu, *Allium mara-schicum* Koçyigit & Özhatay, *Allium marathasicum* Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium mareoticum* Bornm. & Gauba, *Allium margaritae* B.Fedtsch, *Allium margaritifera* Vved, *Allium marginatum* Janka, *Allium mariae* Bordz, *Allium marmoratum* Seregin, *Allium marschalianum* Vved, *Allium massaes-sylum* Batt. & Trab, *Allium materculae* Bordz, *Allium mauritanicum* Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium maximowiczii* Regel, *Allium megalobulbon* Regel, *Allium meikleanum* Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium melanatherum* Pancic, *Allium melananthum* Coincy, *Allium melanogyne* Greuter, *Allium melitense* (Sommier & Caruana ex Borg) Cif. & Giacom, *Allium melliferum* Traub, *Allium membranaceum* Ownbey ex Traub, *Allium meronense* Fragman & R.M.Fritsch, *Allium meteoricum* Heldr. & Hauskn. ex Halácsy, *Allium mexicanum* Traub, *Allium michaelis* F.O.Khass. & Tojibaev, *Allium michoacanum* Traub, *Allium micranthum* Wendelbo, *Allium microdictyon* Prokh, *Allium microdictyum* Prokh, *Allium microspathum* Ekberg, *Allium minus* (S.O.Yu, S.Lee & W.Lee) H.J.Choi & B.U.Oh, *Allium minutiflorum* Regel, *Allium minutum* Vved, *Allium mirum* Wendelbo, *Allium mirzajevii* Tscholok, *Allium moderense* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium moly* L, *Allium monachorum* Stepanov, *Allium monanthum* Maxim, *Allium mongolicum* Regel, *Allium monophyllum* Vved. ex Czerniak, *Allium montanostep-posum* N.Friesen & Seregin, *Allium montelburzense* R.M.Fritsch, Salmaki & Zarre, *Allium montibaicalense* N.Friesen, *Allium monticola* Davidson, *Allium moschatum* L, *Allium mozaffarianii* Maroofi & R.M.Fritsch, *Allium multibulbosum* Jacq, *Allium*

multiflorum Desf, *Allium munzii* (Traub) McNeal, *Allium myrianthum* Boiss, *Allium najafdaricum* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium nanodes* Airy Shaw, *Allium naqabense* Al-Eisawi & Omar, *Allium narcissiflorum* Vill, *Allium nathaliae* Seregin, *Allium neapolitanum* Cirillo, *Allium nebrodense* Guss, *Allium negevense* Kollmann, *Allium nemrutdaghense* Kit Tan & Sorger, *Allium neriniflorum* (Herb.) G.Don, *Allium nevadense* S.Watson, *Allium nevii* S.Watson, *Allium nevsehirense* Koyuncu & Kollmann, *Allium nevskianum* Vved. ex Wendelbo, *Allium nigrum* L, *Allium noeoanum* Reut. ex Regel, *Allium notabile* Feinbrun, *Allium nuristanicum* Kitam, *Allium nutans* L, *Allium obliquum* L, *Allium obtusum* Lemmon, *Allium occultum* Tzanoud. & Trigas, *Allium ochotense* Prokh, *Allium oleraceum* L, *Allium oliganthum* Kar. & Kir, *Allium olympicum* Boiss, *Allium omeiense* Z.Y.Zhu, *Allium opacum* Rech.f, *Allium ophiophyllum* Vved, *Allium optimae* Greuter, *Allium oreodictyum* Vved, *Allium oreophiloides* Regel, *Allium oreophilum* C.A.Mey, *Allium oreoprasoides* Vved, *Allium oreoprasum* Schrenk, *Allium oreoscordum* Vved, *Allium oreotadzhikorum* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium orestis* Kalpoutz., Trigas & Constantin, *Allium orientale* Boiss, *Allium orientoiranicum* Neshati, Zarre & R.M.Fritsch, *Allium orunbairi* F.O.Khass. & R.M.Fritsch, *Allium oschaninii* O.Fedtsch, *Allium ovalifolium* Hand.-Mazz, *Allium ownbeyi* Traub, *Allium paepalanthoides* Airy Shaw, *Allium palentinum* Losa & P.Monts, *Allium pallasii* Murray, *Allium pamiricum* Wendelbo, *Allium pangasicum* Turak, *Allium paniculatum* L, *Allium panjaoense* Wendelbo, *Allium panormitanum* Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium papillare* Boiss, *Allium paradoxum* (M.Bieb.) G.Don, *Allium parciflorum* Viv, *Allium parishii* S.Watson, *Allium parnassicum* (Boiss.) Halácsy, *Allium parryi* S.Watson, *Allium parvulum* Vved, *Allium parvum* Kellogg, *Allium passeyi* N.H.Holmgren & A.H.Holmgren, *Allium pelagicum* Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium pendulinum* Ten, *Allium peninsulare* Lemmon ex Greene, *Allium*

pentadactyli Brullo, Pavone & Spamp, *Allium perdulce* S.V.Fraser, *Allium permixtum* Guss, *Allium peroninianum* Azn, *Allium perpendiculum* Koçyigit, Özhatay & E.Kaya, *Allium pervestitum* Klovov, *Allium petraeum* Kar. & Kir, *Allium petri* F.O.Khass. & R.M.Fritsch, *Allium pevtzovii* Prokh, *Allium phaneranthrum* Boiss. & Hausskn, *Allium phariense* Rendle, *Allium phitosianum* Brullo, Guglielmo, Pavone, Salmeri & Terrasi, *Allium phrygium* Boiss. & Balansa, *Allium phthioticum* Boiss. & Heldr, *Allium pictistamineum* O.Schwarz, *Allium pilosum* Sm, *Allium platakisii* Tzanoud. & Kypr, *Allium platycaule* S.Watson, *Allium platyspathum* Schrenk, *Allium plummerae* S.Watson, *Allium plurifoliatum* Rendle, *Allium podolicum* Blocki ex Racib. & Szafer, *Allium podolicum* Błocki ex Raciborski & Szafer, *Allium pogonotepalum* Wendelbo, *Allium polyrhizum* Turcz. ex Regel, *Allium ponticum* Miscz. ex Grossh, *Allium popovii* Vved, *Allium potosiense* Traub, *Allium praecox* Brandegee, *Allium praemixtum* Vved, *Allium prattii* C.H.Wright, *Allium proponticum* Stearn & Özhatay, *Allium prostratum* Trevir, *Allium protensum* Wendelbo, *Allium pruinatum* Link ex Spreng, *Allium przewalskianum* Regel, *Allium psebaicum* Mikheev, *Allium pseudoalbidum* N.Friesen & Özhatay, *Allium pseudoampeloprasum* Miscz. ex Grossh, *Allium pseudobodeanum* R.M.Fritsch & Matin, *Allium pseudocalypttratum* Mouterde, *Allium pseudoflavum* Vved, *Allium pseudofraseri* T.M.Howard, *Allium pseudohollandicum* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium pseudojaponicum* Makino, *Allium pseudophaneranthrum* Rech.f, *Allium pseudosenescens* H.J.Choi & B.U.Oh, *Allium pseudostamineum* Kollmann & Shmida, *Allium pseudostrictum* Albov, *Allium pseudowinklerianum* R.M.Fritsch & F.O.Khass, *Allium pskemense* B.Fedtsch, *Allium pueblanum* Traub, *Allium pumilum* Vved, *Allium punctum* L.F.Hend, *Allium purpureoviride* Koyuncu & I.Genç, *Allium pustulosum* Boiss. & Hausskn, *Allium pycnotrichum* Trigas, Kalpoutz & Constantin, *Allium pyrenaicum* Costa & Vayr, *Allium ramosum* L, *Allium rausii* Brullo, Guglielmo, Pavone, Salmeri & Terrasi, *Allium ravenii* F.O.Khass.,

Shomur. & Kadyrov, *Allium rechingeri* Wendelbo, *Allium regelianum* A.K.Becker, *Allium regelii* Trautv, *Allium registanicum* Wendelbo, *Allium remediorum* (R.M.Fritsch) R.M.Fritsch, *Allium retrorsum* (Özhatay & Kollmann) Brullo, Guglielmo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium reuterianum* Boiss, *Allium rhabdotum* Stearn, *Allium rhetoreanum* Nábelek, *Allium rhizomatum* Wooton & Standl, *Allium rhodiaceum* Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium rhodopeum* Velen, *Allium rhynchogynum* Diels, *Allium rinae* F.O.Khass., Shomur. & Tojibaev, *Allium ritsi* Iatroú & Tzanoud, *Allium robertianum* Kollmann, *Allium robin-sonii* L.F.Hend, *Allium roborowskianum* Regel, *Allium robustum* Kar. & Kir, *Allium rollovi* Grossh, *Allium rosenbachianum* Regel, *Allium rosenorum* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium roseum* L, *Allium rothii* Zucc, *Allium rotundum* L, *Allium roylei* Stearn, *Allium rubellum* M.Bieb, *Allium rubens* Schrad. ex Willd, *Allium rubriflorum* (Adamovic) Anackov, N.Friesen & Seregin, *Allium rubrovittatum* Boiss. & Heldr, *Allium rude* J.M.Xu, *Allium ruhmerianum* Asch. ex E.A.Durand & Barratte, *Allium rumelicum* Koçyigit & Özhatay, *Allium runemarkii* Trigas & Tzanoud, *Allium runyonii* Ownbey, *Allium rupestre* Steven, *Allium rupestristepposum* N.Friesen, *Allium rupicola* Boiss. ex Mouterde, *Allium sabulosum* Steven ex Bunge, *Allium sabzakense* Wendelbo, *Allium sacculiferum* Maxim, *Allium sahandicum* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium sairamense* Regel, *Allium salinum* A.I.Baranov & Skvortsov, *Allium samniticum* Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium samothracicum* Tzanoud., Strid & Kit Tan, *Allium samurense* Tscholok, *Allium sanbornii* Alph.Wood, *Allium sandrasicum* Kollmann, Özhatay & Bothmer, *Allium sannineum* Gomb, *Allium saposchnikovii* Nikitina, *Allium saralicum* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium sarawschanicum* Regel, *Allium sativum* L, *Allium savii* Parl, *Allium saxatile* M.Bieb, *Allium scabriflorum* Boiss, *Allium scabriscapum* Boiss, *Allium scabriscapum* Boiss. & Kotschy, *Allium schachimardanicum* Vved, *Allium scharobitdinii* F.O.Khass. & Tojibaev, *Allium schergianum* Boiss, *Allium schischkinii* Sobolevsk, *Allium schistosum* N.Friesen

& Seregin, *Allium schmitzii* Cout, *Allium schoenoprasoides* Regel, *Allium schoenoprasum* L, *Allium schrenkii* Regel, *Allium schubertii* Zucc, *Allium schugnanicum* Vved, *Allium scilloides* Douglas ex S.Watson, *Allium scorodoprasum* L, *Allium scorzonerifolium* Desf. ex Redouté, *Allium scotostemon* Wendelbo, *Allium scrobiculatum* Vved, *Allium seirotrichum* Duce. & Maire, *Allium semenovii* Regel, *Allium senescens* L, *Allium serbicum* Vis. & Pancic, *Allium sergii* Vved, *Allium serpentanicum* I.Genç & Özhatay, *Allium serra* McNeal & Ownbey, *Allium setifolium* Schrenk, *Allium severtzovioides* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium sewerzowi* Regel, *Allium sharsmithiae* (Ownbey & Aase ex Traub) McNeal, *Allium shatakiense* Rech.f, *Allium shelkovnikovi* Grossh, *Allium shevockii* McNeal, *Allium shirnakiense* Behçet & Rüstem, *Allium sibthorpiatum* Schult. & Schult.f, *Allium siculum* Ucria, *Allium sinaiticum* Boiss, *Allium sindjarense* Boiss. & Hausskn. ex Regel, *Allium sinkiangense* F.T.Wang & Y.C.Tang, *Allium sintenisii* Freyn, *Allium siphonanthum* J.M.Xu, *Allium sipyleum* Boiss, *Allium siskiyouense* Ownbey ex Traub, *Allium sivasicum* Özhatay & Kollmann, *Allium sochense* R.M.Fritsch & U.Turak, *Allium songpanicum* J.M.Xu, *Allium sordidiflorum* Vved, *Allium sosnovskyanum* Misch. ex Grossh, *Allium spathaceum* Steud. ex A.Rich, *Allium spathulatum* F.O.Khass. & R.M.Fritsch, *Allium speculae* Ownbey & Aase, *Allium sphaerocephalon* L, *Allium spicatum* (Prain) N.Friesen, *Allium spirale* Schweigg, *Allium spirophyllum* Wendelbo, *Allium splendens* Willd. ex Schult. & Schult.f, *Allium sprengeri* Regel, *Allium spurium* G.Don, *Allium stamineum* Boiss, *Allium staticiforme* Sm, *Allium stearnianum* Koyuncu, Özhatay & Kollmann, *Allium stearnii* Pastor & Valdés, *Allium stellatum* Nutt. ex Ker Gawl, *Allium stellerianum* Willd, *Allium stenopetalum* Boiss. & Kotschy ex Regel, *Allium stephanophorum* Vved, *Allium stipitatum* Regel, *Allium stocksianum* Boiss. *Allium stoloniferum* Ownbey & T.D.Jacobson, *Allium stracheyi* Baker, *Allium straussii* Bornm, *Allium strictum* Schrad, *Allium struzlianum* Ogan,

Allium stylosum O.Schwarz, Allium suaveolens Jacq, Allium subakaka Razyfard & Zarre, Allium subangulatum Regel, Allium subhirsutum L, Allium subkopetdagense (R.M.Fritsch & F.O.Khass.) R.M.Fritsch, Allium subnotabile Wendelbo, Allium subtilissimum Ledeb, Allium subvillosum Salzm. ex Schult & Schult.f, Allium sulphureum Vved, Allium suworowi Regel, Allium svetlanae Vved. ex Filim, Allium synnotia G.Don, Allium szovitsii Regel, Allium taciturnum Vved, Allium taeniopetalum Popov & Vved, Allium taishanense J.M.Xu, Allium talassicum Regel, Allium talijevii Klovov, Allium talyschense Miscz. ex Grossh, Allium tanguticum Regel, Allium taquetii H.Lév. & Vaniot, Allium tardans Greuter & Zahar, Allium tardiflorum Kollmann & Shmida, Allium tarkhankuticum Seregin, Allium tatyanae F.O.Khass. & F.Karimov, Allium tauricola Boiss, Allium tchihatschewii Boiss, Allium tekesicola Regel, Allium telavivense Eig, Allium telaponense Traub, Allium telmatum Bogdanovic, Brullo, Giusso & Salmeri, Allium tenuicaule Regel, Allium tenuissimum L, Allium teretifolium Regel, Allium texanum .M.Howard, Allium textile A.Nelson & J.F.Macbr, Allium therinanthum C.Brullo, Brullo, Fragman, Giusso & Salmeri, Allium thessalicum Brullo, Pavone, Salmeri & Tzanoud, Allium thunbergii G.Don, Allium tianschanicum Rupr, Allium tingitanum Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, Allium togashii H.Hara, Allium tokaliense Kamelin & Levichev, Allium tolmiei Baker, Allium tourneuxii Chabert, Allium trachycoleum Wendelbo, Allium trachyoscordum Vved, Allium transvestiens Vved, Allium traubii T.M.Howard, Allium trautvetterianum Regel, Allium tribracteatum Torr, Allium trichocnemis J.Gay, Allium tricoccum Aiton, Allium trifoliatum Cirillo, Allium trifurcatum (F.T.Wang & Tang) J.M.Xu, Allium tripedale Trautv, Allium tripterum Nasir, Allium triquetrum L, Allium truncatum (Feinbrun) Kollmann & D.Zohary, Allium tschimganicum B.Fedtsch, Allium tschulaktavicum Bajtenov & Nelina, Allium tubergeni Freyn, Allium tuberosum Rottlerex Spreng, Allium tubiflorum Rendle, Allium tuchalense F.O.Khass. & Noroozi, Allium

tulipifolium Ledeb, *Allium tuncelianum* (Kollmann) Özhatay, B.Mathew & Siraneci, *Allium tuolumnense* (Ownbey & Aase ex Traub) S.S.Denison & McNeal, *Allium turcicum* Özhatay & Cowley, *Allium turcomanicum* Regel, *Allium turkestanicum* Regel, *Allium turtschicum* Regel, *Allium tuvinicum* (N.Friesen) N.Friesen, *Allium tythocephalum* Schult. & Schult.f, *Allium tythanthum* Vved, *Allium tzanoudakisanum* Brullo, Pavone & Salmeri, *Allium ubipetrense* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium ubsicola* Regel, *Allium umbilicatum* Boiss, *Allium undulatipetalum* I.Genç & Özhatay, *Allium unifolium* Kellogg, *Allium urmiense* Kamelin & Seisums, *Allium ursinum* L, *Allium urusakiorum* Özhatay, Seregin & N.Friesen, *Allium valdecallosum* Maire & Weiller, *Allium valentinae* Pavlov, *Allium validum* S.Watson, *Allium vallivanchense* R.M.Fritsch & N.Friesen, *Allium variegatum* Boiss, *Allium vasilevskajae* Ogan, *Allium vavilovii* Popov & Vved, *Allium verticillatum* Regel, *Allium vescum* Wendelbo, *Allium victoralis* L, *Allium victoris* Vved, *Allium vineale* L, *Allium vinicolor* Wendelbo, *Allium virgunculae* F.Maek. & Kitam, *Allium viridiflorum* Pobed, *Allium viridulum* Ledeb, *Allium vodopjanovae* N.Friesen, *Allium vvedenskyanum* Pavlov, *Allium wallichii* Kunth, *Allium warzobicum* Kamelin, *Allium wendelboanum* Kollmann, *Allium wendelboi* Matin, *Allium weschniakowi* Regel, *Allium wiedemannianum* Regel, *Allium willea-num* Holmboe, *Allium winklerianum* Regel, *Allium woronowii* Misch. ex Grossh, *Allium xiangchengense* J.M.Xu, *Allium xichuanense* J.M.Xu, *Allium xiphopetalum* Aitch. & Baker, *Allium yanchiense* J.M.Xu, *Allium yildirimlii* Dural, Bagci & Ertugrul, *Allium yongdengense* J.M.Xu, *Allium yosemitense* Eastw, *Allium yuanum* F.T.Wang & Tang, *Allium zagricum* R.M.Fritsch, *Allium zaissanicum* Kotukhov, *Allium zaprjagajevii* Kassacz, *Allium zebdanense* Boiss. & Noë, *Allium zergericum* F.O.Khass. & R.M.Fritsch,

The genus *Allium* L. is presented here by 112 species and 4 subspecies occupying the third position among the super-polymorphous genera (behind *Astragalus* L. and

Cousinia Cass.). The use of especially tasteful *Allium* species has a long tradition in Central Asia with apparently deep historical roots. People living in desert and mountainous zones are collecting and using bulbs and leaves in order to prepare special dishes as well as for sale. People in urban areas are buying the required plant material on the local markets. Traditionally, people are cultivating in every home gardens not only *A. cepa* L., *A. sativum* L. (rarely *A. porrum* L., *A. ramosum* L.) but not rarely wild species (*A. suworowii*, *A. oschaninii*, *A. pskemense*) as well. During 2002-2006 several collecting and ethnobotanical research missions have been undertaken in the mountainous zone of Western Tian-Shan, Western Pamiroalaj, as well as in the Kyzylkum desert. About 25 men have been interviewed for use of wild alliums for food and medicine. Mostly old wise men and shepherds had a good knowledge about the use of each wild onion species in the countryside. The knowledge of such kind of information is clearly decreasing, because only few old persons in each village could give any realistic information. These results confirmed the information about use of several species obtained by Umarov and Khassanov 15 years ago [1].

Discussion. Depending on geographical position (desert or mountains) people in the countryside are collecting and using different wild *Allium* species as food. The most important edible species in the mountains are:

1. *A. motor* Kamelin et Levichev
2. *A. costatovaginatatum* Kamelin et Levichev
3. *A. severtzovioides* R.M. Fritsch
4. *A. oschaninii* O. Fedtsch.
5. *A. praemixtum* Vved.
6. *A. pskemense* B. Fedtsch.
7. *A. sativum* L. = *A. longicuspis* Regel
8. *A. filidens* Regel
9. *A. suworowii* Regel
10. *A. stipitatum* Regel

11. *A. rosenorum* R.M. Fritsch, *A. motor*, *A. severtzovioides*, and *A. costatovaginatatum* (from subgenus *Melano-crommyum*) are endemic species of West Tian-Shan area used (young leaves only) in the spring time. Local people say that these alliums are tasteful and very helpful after long cold winter giving strength and rising bloodpressure. Tufts of *A. motor* can be found in May on every market in Tashkent district. During the last 10 years one could buy it easily on Tashkent markets as well. For decades this species was collected in large amounts, and “anzur” became really rare. Nowadays this species is no longer endangered. The same should be true for *A. suworowii*. Another group of important edible wild onions belongs to subgenus *Cepa* and represents close relatives of *A. cepa* (after *A. vavilovii* Popov et Yved. from Koppeh-Dagh and *A. asarense* R.M. Fritsch et Matin from Northern Iran). *Allium oschaninii*, *A. praemixtum* and *A. pskemense* are also cultivated. Local people are cooking meat for every meal using bulbs of these alliums. Therefore, these species became very rare and have been included in all three editions of the “Red Data Book of Uzbekistan” [2, 3, 4]. Nevertheless, people still are collecting them every year. For example, in the mid of 20th century *A. praemixtum* was sold on the markets in Khodzhand and Farish, as well as *A. vavilovii* in Ashgabad.

12. *A. aflatunense* B. Fedtsch

13. *A. atosangineum* Schrenk

14. *A. caesium* Schrenk

15. *A. renardii* Regel

16. *A. tashkenticum* F. O. Khass. et R. M. Fritsch

17. *A. kaufmannii* Regel

18. *A. brevidentiforme* VwQd

19. *A. griffithianum* Boiss

20. *A. turkestanicum* Regel

21. *A. karataviense* Regel

22. *A. crystallinum* Vved

23. *A. drobovii* Vved

24. *A. barszczewskii* Lipsky

25. *A. jodanthum* Vved

26. *A. longiradiatum* Vved

27. *A. sarawschanicum* Regel

28. *A. komarowii* Lipsky

29. *A. turcomanicum* Regel

30. *A. giganteum* Regel (In the desert area not too much *Allium* species are present, and local people are using all species instead of garlic and onion.

31. *A. sabulosum* Stev. This species is added to the camel milk.

32. *M. Bieb.* (*zhua A. caspium* (Pall.)).

33. *A. kyzylkumi* Kamelin

34. *A. borszczowii* Regel

35. *A. aff. filidens* Regel

36. *A. rinae* F.O. Khass. ined. [1]

Conclusion. In addition, the expansion of the scale of human activity in the area causes the transformation of natural pastures, which is associated with an increase in the share of alien and poisonous species. Accordingly, it is of great scientific and practical importance to assess the modern condition of pastures in mountain and sub-mountain areas, to determine changes in pastures related to human influence, to reveal the ecological situation and to develop protection measures [4]. So, some of the species of *Allium* L. are useful as a drug source for human body.

According to the World Health Organization, 60% of available drugs are produced from medicinal plant raw materials. Raw material resources of naturally growing medicinal plants are also limited, and to study their protection, bioecological properties, planned use from raw resources and reproduction of raw materials are one of the urgent problems. Therefore, it is necessary to provide the needs of the pharmaceutical industry with raw materials by medicinal plants in Uzbekistan, to

enrich the local flora with new introducible plant species and to develop technologies for their cultivation [3].

We think to held the investigation on the *Allium* L. species in the south parts of Uzbekistan is the essential in the process of desertification.

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